

Mechanism for the Formation of a National Model of Tourism

Zikriyayev Faxriddin¹

¹ Researcher of Gulistan state university

Annotation:

Currently, the development of tourism, attracting investments in the industry, increasing the capacity of personnel is an urgent task. Tourism in the Republic is often limited within the framework of ancient cities, historical and cultural monuments. There is great potential for the development of tourism in the unique nature of the country, national reserves, mountainous areas. In particular, the development of medical tourism, pilgrimage tourism and ecotourism provides a great impetus not only to the development of the economy, but also to the development of social spheres. In this scientific research work, the issues of the formation of the national model of tourism in Uzbekistan are discussed.

Keywords: tourism, tourism market, types of tourism, national model.

Introduction. Tourism is a certain phenomenon to all of us. Since the emergence of mankind, its representatives or groups have traveled to one or another continent of the planet, to the lands, countries on the continents. Only by our time tourism has become a special economic and social sphere, which, of course, requires management that is unique.

Objects and research methods. Currently, there are mainly two main tasks in tourism:

1. to put market relations into practice in tourism and enrich these relations with content;
2. to perceive the change in secular relations in tourism as a timely novelty.

The first of the task is extremely important in the development of our country's tourism. Because the tourism market itself is still in an unformed state. This is a wide, multifaceted process, in which the organization of the market and filling the market with tourism products itself is very heavy, time-consuming and knowledge-intensive.

Since buyers, consumers of goods and services in the tourism market are changing, maintaining the competitiveness of these market products, selling and solving many other problems are also demanding to develop a management system that is unique in tourism.

Results and its discussion. In the world economy, tourism has become one of the most productive. Tourism routes are mainly ecological routes that include elements of historical-recreational, historical-cultural heritage sites, wellness tourism. It is important to develop other areas of Tourism. In the activities of firms and companies in the field of tourism, it is advisable to establish a wider path for the entry of tourists from abroad into Uzbekistan. The main reasons for this will lead to a further increase in the position of Uzbekistan in foreign countries, the creation of additional jobs, the entry of foreign currencies, an increase in the share of tourism in the gross domestic product, in the revenue part of the state budget, and the creation of a number of amenities. From this point of view, innovation and financial and investment complexes, marketing research are of particular importance in the general system of strategic management of companies and firms, which are specialized in providing tourism services operating in our republic [1].

Modern marketing is considered the "weapon" of doing business, in which the following principles are widely used: firstly, the development of products or services at the discretion and demand of consumers; secondly, taking into account the demand of buyers in the entire market, and not buyers, who are likely to buy these products. thirdly, monandically implement marketing activities to business goals.

By applying the principles of Marketing to the management of the tourism industry, it is possible to deliver quality products to consumers, getting rid of the development of non-essential and non-consumer products. In tourism, the product can be "idea", "services" and "goods". The tourism network mainly develops services. Because they are "products that cannot be considered and caught", marketing activities also continue to be complicated. In particular, the "eye progressives" problem complicates quality control. Also, potential buyers also have difficulty assessing the quality of tourism services. If in other areas the product is delivered to consumers in this network, buyers will go to the product, service (region or territory) themselves. In tourism services marketing, the high share of time and funds spent by consumers (tourists) on trips has a huge impact on people's decision-making about tourism. Today, many of the firms serving in the tourism industry are engaged in sending tourists from Uzbekistan to foreign countries, that is, exit tourism. The number of people who use wellness tourism services in particular is increasing from year to year.

It is also advisable to further develop wellness tourism in our country. The availability and rational use of Natural Resources in the development of this area. Of particular importance in this area is the training of qualified personnel providing quality services and, of course, the research of innovation marketing in attracting investors and consumers, in which the task of marketing is to offer the necessary product (or service) to customers, to the market. In this sense, marketing is art and science. By applying Marketing principles to the management of the tourism industry, consumers are divided into delivering quality products, getting rid of the development of non-essential and non-consumer products. In tourism services marketing, the high share of time and funds spent by consumers (tourists) on trips has a big impact on people making decisions about tourism. To ensure that all activities and goals are shared in the tourism business, it is necessary to develop a marketing plan [2].

This plan serves to effectively distribute all available resources, time and funds in marketing decision-making marketing in tourism the most important area of application of technology is to carry out research in order to increase the possibilities of the country or territory in the field of tourism, to promote access and domestic tourism within its framework. The main tasks to be solved at the time of conducting marketing research in the tourist market are: to analyze the share of the tourism sector in GDP, the necessary measures to increase income in the tourism sector, to identify

the strategic product market and the population layer, to create and improve the reputation of a competitive tourist product in domestic and foreign markets.

Model marketing research of the tourist market, which is organized at the level of the state and market entity, consists in collecting information (primary and secondary) in order to perform the following tasks:

- study of the composition of the offer in the tourist market;
- determination of the priority level of the tourist sector for the economic system of the country (territory) ;
- conduct an analysis of the flow of domestic, incoming and outgoing tourists;
- determination of the scope of vital and main problems in the tourist sector of the country (territory) ;
- determination of the circle of competitors in the tourist market;
- determination of the priority and weaknesses of the tourist product in competition;
- identification of the country's (territory)potential in tourism and identification of strategic markets and population stratification;
- to determine the maximum effective position of the firm in the tourist market.

The main issue that a tourist enterprise must solve before conducting marketing research in the tourist market is to determine the method of data collection, which maximally reflects the true state of affairs in the industry, as well as to bring the indicators used in data collection and processing into one system. Scientific research on the tourism industry, lack of statistical data – the main reason for the problems that arise when obtaining accurate information about the state of demand and supply in the tourist market [3].

The strategic goal of tourism development is to create a modern network of tourist services, develop the tourism industry and use the cultural potential of the regions by attracting investments, including foreign ones.

The concept of tourism development in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period up to 2030 covers the following issues:

- improvement of the regulatory framework in the field of tourist activity, aimed at creating favorable conditions for the functioning of business entities in the field of tourism;
- development of tourism infrastructure and its accompanying infrastructure in all regions of the Republic, based on the needs of tourists;
- improve the quality of transportation services provided, expand internal and external transportation routes, develop transport infrastructure;
- development of passenger transport system between Central Asian countries;
- diversification of tourist products and services aimed at different segments of the tourist market;
- development of domestic tourism, which promotes the promotion of the activity of the subjects of tourist activities, aimed at fanning the need for tourist services within the country;
- promotion of tourist products of the Republic of Uzbekistan in domestic and foreign markets;
- improving the system of training and retraining of employees of subjects of tourist activity, training of highly qualified specialists for the field.

While foreign investments are treated with special respect in Uzbek tourism, it is necessary to emphasize that foreign investments should be "additional" to domestic investments in order to successfully solve the problems facing the industry. Only in this case can they have a stimulating effect on the development of Tourism. In addition, world experience shows that the volume of foreign direct investments almost never exceeds 10-12% of total investments in the national economy.

Foreign investments in the tourism sector have the following advantages [4], [5]:

- the positive impact of foreign investments on the tourism economy in a holistic way;
- increased direct capital flows to the non-productive sector of the country's economy;
- growth of local entrepreneurship in tourism;
- enterprises in the regional tourism infrastructure are located in the country;
- increased international competitiveness;
- promoting the creation of new jobs for the population;
- improving the living and cultural level of the population;
- labor resources (education system and training of tourist personnel);
- to have know-how in management and technology.

In order to create a favorable regime for foreign investors, it is required to carry out fundamental changes in state policy in the field of attracting, protecting and using foreign investments, providing foreign investors with stability, guarantees and conditions of non-discrimination in the country.

An important step in increasing investment in tourism infrastructure should be to create a truly favorable investment environment for the wide involvement of tourist entrepreneurs in the process. First of all, it concerns the implementation of preferential credit policy on a long-term basis (from three to seven years), including loan repayment, the development of the guarantee system of financial and credit institutions, inviolability of property rights, the simplification of the rules for transferring dividends to foreign investors, preferential tax policy on profit, further development of the material base of tourism, etc.

The main positive aspect of the impact of foreign investments on the economy of the host country is its impact on the level of Investiture activity in the country and, consequently, on the increase in economic growth. If the country does not have enough investment resources or they are limited in the economy in one whole or in certain industries, foreign investments partially fill the investment gap. Investition increased activity leads to an increase in GDP.

Conclusion. According to the results of the study, the country's tourist potential is not fully used, the creation of conditions for quality recreation for local and foreign citizens on the territory of Uzbekistan requires a more active implementation of state policy in the field of tourism.

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